

Scientific Orientation of Youth as the Basis of Formation of a New University Culture

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Abstract—At present the process of formation of corporate values in Kazakh universities is under the influence of a whole range of socio-economic and cultural changes: on the one hand universities must maintain and transmit traditional cultural values of education, on the other, to improve quality of service and to involve young people to science, providing thus own competitiveness. Thus, this article presents some results of two cycles of sociological research conducted in 2012 and aimed at identifying possible ways to popularize science and readiness to participate of youth in given activities, expectations of young scientists and the prospects of future development of the Kazakh science.

Keywords—Corporate culture, higher education institutions, motivation reforms, young scientists.

I. INTRODUCTION

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In modern society, the system of corporate culture and values is based on the principles of integration of university education with scientific research and development, on openness for interaction with government, business, consumers and the international community, on innovation in all spheres of activity, on the academic autonomy; on variability of educational programs and continuity of the educational and research processes [1].

The presence of strong corporate culture is one of the factors influencing the competitiveness of universities. Success in a competitive educational market is provided to higher educational institutions that have a clear concept and strategy of its development, focused primarily on providing high quality of specialist training, the creation of a positive image and reputation of both the university and its alumni. Modern HEIs should consider the corporate culture as a key and a powerful strategic tool that allows directing all

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departments and individuals to solve common tasks, to mobilize the initiative of employees and ensure their effective interaction [2].

The development of scientific research and layouts, professional preparation of the younger generation is an indication of maturity of the corporate values system of the University, and the success of functioning of Kazakhstani science depends on formation of the youth's professional competencies that are in demand in conditions of innovative economy, of knowledge society and the global labor market.

The results of two cycles of sociological research, conducted in seven regions of Kazakhstan: Astana, Almaty, Western Kazakhstan region, Aktobe region, South Kazakhstan region, Karaganda region, the East Kazakhstan region.

Sampling frame of 1st cycle of the research - 1500 respondents, the target group consisted of young people aged 16 to 29 years, living in Kazakhstan.

Sampling frame of 2nd cycle of the research was 500 respondents (2.5% of the population), allowed to represent the population in the main socio-demographic characteristics. Target group of research consisted of young professionals under the age of 40 years, working in research institutions and organizations, higher education institutions or enrolled in post-graduate education (master's and doctorate).

During the preparation of the research a combined, multi-sampling was applied. At the stage of scientific institutions selection quota sample has been applied. At the stage of selection of units in institutions - cluster sampling was applied (as clusters faculties, departments, divisions, and sections were used). At the stage of selection of respondents' interval random sampling based on lists of personnel was used.

II. RESULTS OF THE 1ST CYCLE: EVALUATION OF CHANGES

Considering the transformation process the higher education system it should be noted that the overall aim of the educational reforms in Kazakhstan is the adaptation of the education system to the new socio-economic conditions and challenges. Education is recognized as one of the most important priorities of long-term of the Strategy “Kazakhstan - 2050”. Improving the education system plays an important role in achieving this goal.

In considering this issue taking advantage of sociological methodology allowed to describe the subjective perception of the reforms in the education sector of direct participants involved in the process - in this case, students. It can be noted that, in the field of innovative transformations, there is an inverse dependence, expressed in the fact that a positive

attitude and endorsement of innovation, promotes their full and speedy promotion.

During the survey students were asked “Do you believe that reforms in the higher education system in Kazakhstan are moving in the right direction or are they went the wrong way to a large extent?”

Fig. 1 Diagram “Public opinion on the direction of reforms in education”

Students’ evaluation of character of the changes in the education process proves the positive dynamics of occurring transformations.

The graphic in Fig. 1 shows a pooled estimates of reform directions, which show that more than 60% of respondents are confident in the correctness of changes taking place.

TABLE I

EVALUATION OF THE DEGREE OF REALIZATION OF PRIORITY OBJECTIVES IN REFORMATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION RK (IN% OF TOTAL RESPONDENTS)

1. Creating the conditions for the development of educational programs	Yes- 68.5% No- 15.4% Nothing to say- 15.9%
2. The development of creative, spiritual and physical capabilities of personality	Yes - 54.7% No - 26.7% Nothing to say - 18.6%
3. Upbringing of civicism and patriotism	Yes - 52.5% No - 29.8% Nothing to say - 17.7%
4. An introduction to the achievements of cultures	Yes - 54.1% No - 24.6% Nothing to say - 21.3%
5. Expansion of International Relations	Yes - 62.8% No - 17.7% Nothing to say - 19.5%
6. Implementation of new educational technologies	Yes - 63.8% No - 18.6% Nothing to say - 17.9%
7. Informatization of education	Yes - 61.3% No - 18.2% Nothing to say - 20.5%
8. Preparation of qualified specialists	Yes - 55.5% No - 23.2% Nothing to say - 21.3%
9. Re-training of personnel	Yes - 55.5% No - 25.5% Nothing to say - 31.4%

Students who participated in the survey were asked to note which of the priorities of the education system are realized

and which are not. As main tasks to assess the respondents were offered following educational and instructional objectives:

- Creating conditions for the adoption of educational programs;
- Development of creative, spiritual, and physical capacities of the personality;
- Upbringing of citizenship and patriotism;
- An introduction to cultural achievements;
- Expansion of international relations;
- Introduction of new learning technologies;
- Informatization of Education;
- Preparation of qualified professionals;
- Retraining of and re-education of personnel.

The data in Table I show that, in the opinion of students there is consistent implementation of strategic tasks on the highlighted areas. Not a single position presented for consideration, did not score less than 50% of positive responses [3].

III. RESULTS OF 2ND CYCLE OF THE RESEARCH: PATH IN SCIENCE AND MOTIVATION OF PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY OF YOUNG SCIENTISTS

The distribution of young scientists’ answers to the question “When did you decide to do science?” shows that the relative majority of respondents came to the decision in the process of obtaining the basic professional education - 33.3%, and after finishing university - 22.9%.

Next choice of respondents is “after joining the university or research institutes” - 14.4%.

The lowest numerical index - young Kazakhs who have decided to devote themselves to professional science at school - 11.4%. At the same time, it should be noted that this figure has grown almost 2 times (6.8% in 2008).

There are no distinctly expressed correlation dependencies between the decision to choose scientific activity and the main socio-demographic parameters of research sample. 17.8% of respondents could not answer the question.

During research it was also intended to specify an overview of the way of young scientists in the professional science by identifying the basic motives of involvement in the scientific and research activities.

Respondents were asked two interrelated questions:

“Why did you choose to do science?”

“Why do you do science?”

Answers to the question about the primary motives of pursuit of science of young scientists distributed as follows:

- On the results of frequency distribution in the first place is the answer “at own will” - 54.2%.
- Slightly less, 1/5 of the respondents came to science because of the circumstances.
- 15.5% expressed a desire to contribute to the development of Kazakhstan.
- 10.6% seek professional growth and satisfaction of spiritual needs.

– “To meet the material needs” answer option was chosen only 4.6% of respondents.

9.4% found it difficult to describe the motives of their professional activities.

In general, it can be noted a tendency among young Kazakh scientists of awareness of the choice of their professional path. 80% of respondents came to the science consciously realizing their spiritual needs, abilities, and patriotic feelings.

The number of specialists, whose choice was largely predetermined by the circumstances in general is not large, and remains almost unchanged since 2008 - 21.9%.

Answers to the question “Why do you do science?” confirm the predominance of motives of creativity, searching for ways of self-realization and implementation of an active civic and patriotic position among professional motivation of young scientists.

“Interest” is the main motive for one third of the respondents engaged in science. Among the main reasons should also be identified the “possibility of creativity” - 18.7% and “desire to contribute to society and country” - 18.7%.

Deserves special attention the answer “source of livelihood”, that was selected by every fifth respondent. Over the past 4 years, the figure has increased more than 2 times.

IV. SCENARIOS OF THE FUTURE: PLANS AND EXPECTATIONS

Establishing a plan for the future, $\frac{3}{4}$ of young scientists show activity not only in continuing its research and development activities, but also hope to brisk it up. The young scientists were invited to respond to the question “Do you agree with the statement that science - is the main activity of my life?”

51.4% of young scientists agree with this statement: 15.2% of them agree completely, and another 36.2% expressed a partial agreement by selecting the answer “more likely than not.”

18.1% of respondents believe that statement to a greater extent is incorrect. 6.8% strongly disagree. The total negative score is - 24.9%. Found it difficult to answer - 23.5% of respondents.

V. THE PRESTIGE OF SCIENTIST AND SCIENTIFIC ACTIVITY

As discussed above, the prestige of the profession of scientist is not a system-forming motivation for young scientists, deciding to choose it as a profession.

This issue has been considered separately in the research. These results allow considering, if not a significant increase in the prestige of science, but a clearly defined trend, that indicates a gradual increase in the understanding of the role and importance of science in society.

As a result of a public opinion poll it was identified that an equal number of young scientists believed that science is a prestigious profession and vice versa, being sure that it is not.

22.4% of young scientists believe that scientist career is a prestigious one (has increased 2 times - 11.1% since 2008).

22.7% - chose the answer “No” (the figure decreased for more than 10% over the past 4 years - 33.4%).

VI. CONCLUSION

Thus, the results of the survey showed that the scientific potential of youth is an indicator of the competitiveness of the university as a social and economic system. Major part of the young scientists who participated in the interviews, note the significant rise in the Kazakh science. The strongest aspects in the development of Kazakhstani science interviewers note government support of science, growth of grant funding for science, the emergence of funding new sources, both personally for scientists and resources for further research.

Attainment of material wealth, building scientific or academic career, the presence of interesting work, independence and demand are indicators of life success of young scientists. Sense of their relevance as professional is an important part of personal self-esteem of a young scientist that significantly affects the future plans and professional guidelines.

For the large part of the young scientists of Kazakhstan are not alien to the basic ideas of market reforms: social and economic initiative, enterprise, a high level of claims regarding education and science, the desire to engaged in favorite business, commitment, focus on own forces and personal success.

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